

A STUDY OF THE HYDROGEN BONDING IN *o*-NITROPHENOL IN PRESENCE OF *p*-NITROPHENOL

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The individual polarograms of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols in the p_R range of 1.0 to 10.2 have been studied. The polarograms of mixtures of the two phenols at p_R 10.2 and 2.0 have also been studied. These consist of single waves and are of similar pattern, and exhibit residual current region.

With increasing amounts of *o*-nitrophenol in an excess of *p*-nitrophenol or *vice versa*, the wave-heights increase gradually, although the value is less than the sum total of the individual wave-heights. Thus, a mutual influence of the two substances in mixtures is observed, the influence of the *ortho* compound over the *para*-isomer being less than the reverse.

The stability of the H-bonding in *o*-nitrophenol varies with the proportional amount of *p*-nitrophenol. The influence of *para* over the *ortho* compound results in the destabilisation of the H-bonding in the latter.

Ortho- and *para*-nitrophenols have been studied by several workers (Shikata *et al.*, *J. Appl. Chem. Japan*, 1928, 4, 924; *Mem. Coll. Agr. Kyoto Imp. Univ.*, 1931, 17, 121; Astle and McConnell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 35, 2395; Pearson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 692; 1949, 45, 199; Page *et al.*, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1949, 53, 545). *o*-Nitrophenol possesses a H-bonded structure which is absent in the *p*-isomer, and this difference accounts for the variation in their melting point and solubility ("Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 1952; Carric, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 628) and complex formation (Phillip, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 820; 1924, 125, 527). As any other factor, the presence of *para*-isomer is likely to influence the formation and stability of the H-bonding in *o*-nitrophenol, and hence, a polarographic study of the above influence has been undertaken.

For a study of such influence, a knowledge of the polarographic behaviour of individual substances is necessary. The earlier workers differ in their results and views, e.g. Page *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report that *ortho*-nitrophenol is reduced to the $-NH_2$ -compound in acid media in one stage, while Pearson (*loc. cit.*) reports that this takes place in two stages. Astle and McConnell (*loc. cit.*) point out that *ortho*-nitrophenol is reduced to $-NHOH$ stage alone in acid media, which is attributed to the stabilisation of this product by H-bond (Sidgwick, "Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen Compounds", 1942, p. 268). But Pearson points out that the above H-bonded structure is reducible further. In neutral solutions, while Page *et al.* report the reduction of *ortho*-nitrophenol in one stage to $-NHOH$ only, others do not report about the nature of the reduction in this medium. As regards reduction of *p*-nitrophenol, while Page *et al.* report a 6e reduction in acid media in one stage (*i.e.* to $-NH_2$ stage), Pearson reports reduction in two stages as in nitrobenzene (Shikata, *Trans. Faraday*

Soc., 1925, 21, 42, 53). These workers differ also in the values of their half-wave potentials and the slopes of the p_H -half-wave potential curves.

On account of such divergent results the present authors have studied the two nitrophenols first individually and then* in mixtures under identical sets of conditions with the equipment available.

EXPERIMENTAL

Individual Phenols

A manual type of polarograph, supplied by Adept Laboratories, Poona, was used for the investigation. It consists of the usual features, viz., potential divider, galvanometer, the dropping mercury electrode and the polarographic cell. The circuit diagram involved is the usual one. The capillary characteristic is $1.373 \text{ mg.}^2/\text{sec.}^{1/2}$, the drop time being 3.8 secs. An Ayrton shunt 1/20 was used in all the studies except where otherwise indicated. The galvanometer sensitivity was $4.3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ amp./cm.}$

All experiments were carried out with $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ stock solutions of the nitrophenols in 10% ethanol. The test solution consisted of 4 c.c. of the stock solution mixed with 4 c.c. of 0.009 % gelatin solution and 12 c.c. of buffer. The measurements were carried out with buffers of p_H 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.2, 4.8, 5.6, 7.2, 8.0, 9.3 and 10.2, the p_H of the buffers being checked by Merc's indicators and charts. Gelatin was included in the solution to suppress maxima.

The test solution was deaerated by bubbling hydrogen for 15 minutes, the dropping mercury electrode dipped into the solution and the polarographic cell connected to a saturated calomel electrode (S.C. E.), used as the reference electrode, by an agar bridge. The temperature of the cell was maintained constant at $27^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The polarogram of the solution was recorded. The diffusion current was measured by extrapolation method. The number of electrons involved in the electrode reaction was evaluated by means of the Ilkovic equation (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1934, 6, 498). The diffusion coefficients of the nitrophenols have been evaluated from the relation

$$D = \frac{2.990 \times 10^{-7}}{\eta(V_m)^{1/2}} \text{ at } 27^\circ$$

where η is the viscosity of the solution and V_m , the molar volume of the nitrophenol. The diffusion coefficients of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols, thus calculated, are 7.254×10^{-6} and $7.290 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.}$ respectively.

Mixtures of o- and p-Nitrophenols

The test solution was prepared by mixing 4 c.c. of the stock solution ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) of *o*-nitrophenol with 1 c.c. of 0.036% gelatin solution and 12 c.c. of buffer of p_H 10.2. To this mixture 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 4 c.c. of *p* nitrophenol solutions ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) were added in successive experiments, and the total volume of the mixture was made up to 20 c.c. The test solution was then deaerated by bubbling hydrogen and the polarograms were recorded.

A set of polarograms with 4 c.c. of the stock solution of *p*-nitrophenol and varying amounts of *o*-nitrophenol solution at the same p_H have also been recorded.

The above two sets of experiments were then performed at p_H 2.0. A few of the polarograms are recorded in Fig. 3. The wave-heights are recorded in cm of the galvanometer scale and this multiplied by 0.86 gives the diffusion current (or wave-height) in microamperes.

Chemically pure substances were employed in all the above studies.

TABLE I

Polarographic study of o- and p-nitrophenols individually in 10% ethanol at various p_H.

p_H .	No. of waves.	Half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) (in volts)		Diffusion current (i_d) (in m. amp.)		No. of electrons (n).	
		1st. step.	2nd. step.	1st. step.	2nd. step.	1st. step.	2nd. step.
A. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol.							
1.0	1	-0.175	...	14.20 × 0.86	...	5.4	...
2.0	1	-0.205	...	11.70	...	4.5	...
3.0	1	-0.290	...	10.70	...	4.1	...
4.2	1	-0.310	...	10.20	...	3.9	...
4.8	1	-0.370	...	11.20	...	4.2	...
5.6	2	-0.410	-0.710	3.00	5.80 × 0.86	1.8	3.4
7.2	1	-0.520	...	9.10	...	3.5	...
8.0	1	-0.560	...	9.00	...	3.5	...
9.3	1	-0.640	...	9.50	...	3.6	...
10.2	1	-0.720	...	9.20	...	3.5	...
B. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenol.							
1.0	1	-0.255	...	15.5 × 0.86	...	5.9	...
2.0	1	-0.330	...	13.0	...	5.0	...
3.0	1	-0.360	...	13.0	...	5.0	...
4.2	1	-0.450	...	12.0	...	4.6	...
4.8	1	-0.490	...	12.0	...	4.6	...
5.6	2	-0.510	-1.010	4.8	7.4 × 0.86	1.8	4.2
7.2	1	-0.670	...	15.3	...	3.9	...
8.0	1	-0.725	...	13.4	...	3.3	...
9.3	1	-0.820	...	11.7	...	4.5	...
10.2	1	-0.990	...	12.6	...	4.1	...

DISCUSSION

Individual Phenols

The half-wave potentials, number of electrons involved in the electrode reaction (n) and the wave-heights are recorded in Table I (A and B). A few of the polarograms are shown in Fig. 1.

The polarograms of both *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols consist of single waves in the p_H range 1.0 to 10.2 except at p_H 5.6, where a double-wave is indicated (vide Fig. 1).

Maxima were observed in good acid media in spite of the presence of gelatin as the maximum suppressor.

FIG. 1
Polarograms of *o*- & *p*-nitrophenols in 10% ethanol
at various p_H :

The half-wave potentials of the two substances increase with p_H and vary linearly (vide Fig. 2), the slopes of the curves being -0.058 and $-0.067V/p_H$ unit respectively for *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols. The half-wave potentials and wave-heights of the *ortho*-compound are always less than those of the *para*-isomer (vide Table I, A and B), and this is attributed to the H-bonding (Sidgwick, *loc. cit.*) in *o*-nitrophenol.

Further, from the values of (n) in Table I, it is evident that *o*-nitrophenol is reduced in one stage to $-NH_2$ at low p_H (1.0 and 2.0) and to $-NHOH$ stage only at p_H 3.0 to 5.0. *p*-Nitrophenol is reduced to $-NH_2$ directly in acid media. Reduction of both the substances proceeds through the intermediary nitroso state at p_H 5.6, the final stage being the $-NHOH$ state in the two cases. Both the substances are reduced at one stage to $-NHOH$ in neutral and alkaline media, *i.e.* from p_H 7.2 to 10.2.

FIG. 2

Effect of p_H on half-wave potential.

Mixture of Phenols

The half-wave potentials and wave-heights of the mixtures of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols at p_H 10.2 and 2.0 are recorded in Table II. The %influence is computed to the sum total of the wave-heights of the two nitrophenols observed separately (vide Table I).

Polarograms at p_H 10.2.—The polarograms of mixtures observed at p_H 10.2 consist of single waves (vide Fig. 3) and are of similar pattern and contain residual current region.

The observed wave-heights are always less than the sum total of the proportional wave-heights of the substances in the mixtures. It is therefore inferred that the above decrease in the wave-heights is due to the influence of one over the other.

Considering the structures of the two substances, *o*-nitrophenol contains a H-bond, whereas the *para*-isomer is devoid of the same. The presence of *ortho*- may have very little influence over *para*-nitrophenol since the stability of the *para*-isomer is greater as compared to that of the *ortho*-isomer, as supported by the physical properties such as m.p. and steam-volatility. *p*-Nitrophenol, however, is likely to influence the stability of *o*-nitrophenol.

In the first set of experiments, wherein varying amounts of *ortho*-phenol are added to a constant amount of *p* isomer, the %influence calculated remains more or less the same (vide Table II, column 4). This shows that there is mutual influence in the mixture of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols and, as shown above, the individual influences are of different magnitude.

Further, where the amount of *p*-nitrophenol is constant, the %influence of *para*- over *ortho* decreases with increasing amount of the latter. At the same time, it may be noted that *para*-nitrophenol being in large quantity, the influence exerted by it over the *ortho*-isomer will be of greater magnitude. Again, with increasing additions of *o*-nitrophenol, its %influence over the *para*-isomer, although of small magnitude, will increase at a certain rate. These two opposing influences would so adjust that a constant overall %influence is exhibited. Similarly, in the second reverse set, of

experiments performed with a constant amount of *o*-nitrophenol and increasing amounts of *p*-nitrophenol, the resultant %influence remains more or less constant, and is of the same order as above (vide Table II, column 8).

FIG. 3

Polarograms of mixtures of *o* & *p*-nitrophenols.

In view of the variations in the amounts of the two substances, the stability of H-bonding in *o*-nitrophenol may not be to the same extent in all the mixtures studied and also may not be of the same order as in *o*-nitrophenol molecule.

If the influence of *para*- over *ortho*-nitrophenol is viewed as resulting in the destabilisation of the H-bonding in the latter, the decreasing influence of *para*- over *ortho*-phenol (*vide supra*) would mean a gradual increase in the stability of *o*-nitrophenol, *i. e.*, the H-bonding is made more stable so that its contribution towards the observed wave-height decreases gradually, as the H-bonding is responsible for the decreased wave-height of *o*-nitrophenol as compared to that of the *p*-isomer (*vide supra*). Similarly, in the reverse set of mixtures, the %influence of *para*- over *ortho*-nitrophenol increases gradually and, hence, the H-bonding in the latter is made less and less stable.

If there were no mutual influence, one would expect a polarogram with a distinct double wave, since the difference in the half-wave potentials, *viz.* 0.27V (*vide Table I*), is sufficient enough to effect a separation of the waves. But the mutual influence resulting in overall %influence (*vide supra*) shows that they are reduced at the

electrode in such a way that the two waves, other wise expected, coalesce, giving rise to a single wave as observed (vide Fig. 3). The polarograms are of similar pattern.

TABLE II

Polarographic study of mixtures of o- & p-nitrophenols at p_n 10.2 and at 2.0.

Amount of <i>p</i> -nitrophenol = 4 c.c.				Amount of <i>o</i> -nitrophenol = 4 c.c.			
Amount of <i>o</i> -nitrophenol. (vs. S.C.F.).	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Obs. i_D .	% Influence.	Amount of <i>p</i> -nitrophenol. (vs. S.C.F.).	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Obs. i_D .	% Influence.
A. At p_n 10.2.							
0.5 c.c.	-0.999 volt	9.45 cm	19.6	0.5 c.c.	-0.730 volt	9.10 cm.	13.6
1.0	-0.970	10.00	22.5	1.0	-0.750	9.70	18.1
1.5	-0.935	10.80	23.1	1.5	-0.765	10.40	21.1
2.0	-0.970	11.90	21.7	2.0	-0.770	11.50	20.7
2.5	-0.887	12.30	24.5	2.5	-0.815	12.10	23.6
3.0	-0.885	13.30	24.0	3.0	-0.825	13.30	22.5
3.5	-0.870	13.80	26.0	3.5	-0.835	13.80	25.3
4.0	-0.880	14.80	25.3	4.0	-0.855	14.70	25.8
Mean 23.4				Mean 22.4			
B. At p_n 2.0.							
0.5	-0.305	11.25	22.3*	0.5	-0.245	11.20	16.0*
1.0	-0.305	13.63	14.4	1.0	-0.255	12.00	19.7
1.5	-0.305	14.50	16.6	1.5	-0.260	12.70	23.4
2.0	-0.300	16.38	13.1	2.0	-0.280	13.80	24.2
2.5	-0.310	17.25	15.1	2.5	-0.280	14.70	25.9
3.0	-0.305	18.75	13.9	3.0	-0.290	14.90	30.5*
3.5	-0.300	15.25	34.4*	3.5	-0.290	15.80	31.5*
4.0	-0.310	18.25	26.1*	4.0	-0.310	18.25	26.1
Mean 14.6				Mean 23.9			

* Not considered in the evaluation of the mean %influence.

As seen from Table II-A, the half-wave potentials of the mixtures at p_n 10.2 vary gradually from a value corresponding to the substance in excess (cf. Table I; $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for *ortho*- and *para* at p_n 10.2 are 0.720V and 0.990V respectively) with increasing amounts of the other. These values for the mixtures suggest that the nature of the mixture changes to a more reducible (vide Table II, column 2) or less reducible (Table II column 6), depending on the amount of *o*-nitrophenol present in the mixture.

Polarograms at p_n 2.0.—The polarograms of mixtures at p_n 2.0 consist of single waves (vide Fig. 3).

As at p_n 10.2, the observed wave-heights are always less than those calculated on the additivity principle. Thus, the mutual influence is exhibited at this p_n as well. Except in one or two mixtures, the %influence remains more or less the same (vide Table II-B) in each set of experiments, the deviations observed being attributed to experimental errors. The order of the %influence is different for the two sets of mixtures unlike at p_n 10.2. This difference is due to the effect of p_n . Also, in the mixtures consisting of 4 c.c. of *o*-nitrophenol and varying amounts of the *para*-isomer,

the %influence increases at a slow rate, unlike at p_n 10.2. This again is due to the acidic nature of the solution.

Regarding the variation of mutual influence in mixtures, the same explanation (vide p_n 10.2) holds good, *i. e.*, *o*-nitrophenol has got little influence over *p*-nitrophenol and the latter possesses an appreciable influence over the *ortho*-isomer in destabilising the H-bonding.

The general characteristics of the polarograms at p_n 2.0 are the same as at p_n 10.2. Unlike at p_n 10.2, the mixtures at p_n 2.0 exhibit different behaviour. The half-wave potentials of mixtures with 4 c.c. of *p*-nitrophenol and varying amounts of *o*-isomer remain more or less the same, *viz.*, $-0.305V$ (vide Table II-B) *i. e.*, the mixtures exhibit a half-wave potential nearer to that of *p*-nitrophenol ($-0.330V$; Table I-B, column 3), indicating thereby that the reducible character remains the same. In other words, *o*-nitrophenol influences the nature of the mixture to a very small extent.

In the reverse set of experiments (vide Table II-B) the half-wave potentials of the mixtures increase gradually from a value nearer to that of *o*-nitrophenol alone ($-0.205V$, vide Table I-A) to a value approaching that of *p*-nitrophenol ($-0.330V$), *i. e.*, the nature of the mixture changes from one of an easily reducible to that of relatively difficultly reducible character.

The authors express their grateful thanks to Prof. S. S. Joshi, D.Sc., for his keen interest and for providing all necessary facilities.

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Received October 16, 1957.